

**SALIVATORY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTROINTESTINAL
ALLERGY IN CHILDREN****Artikova Maksad Makhmudovna**

Bukhara State Medical Institute

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Gastrointestinal allergy (GIA) is characterized by polymorphism of clinical manifestations and complex immunological mechanisms. It has a high and uneven prevalence in various regions of the globe, due to specific dietary traditions and the peculiarity of the impact of environmental factors on the child's body [1].

The study of the features of the immunological profile in digestive secretions (saliva, gastric juice) in a number of gastrointestinal diseases, such as chronic gastroduodenitis, celiac disease, demonstrated high informative indicators of secretory immunity, changes in which reflected the activity and depth of the pathological process in the affected organ [2].

Accumulated scientific knowledge on the study of the biochemical and immunological composition of saliva in various chronic pathologies, including gastrointestinal diseases, stress, has shown the ability of oral secretions to reflect the processes occurring in the patient's body and serve as an adequate substrate for monitoring homeostasis [3].

Analysis of the accumulated material led to the conclusion that the sIgA level reflects the status of local immunity. An increase in the level of sIgA indicates the development of an adaptive immune response aimed at the formation of mechanisms of adaptation to stress, to changes in external conditions [4].

In children with allergopathology, due to the atopic tendency of the immune response, the synthesis of ID-antibodies is increased, which is manifested by their increased level and high frequency of detection with an exacerbation of the allergic process against the background of a decrease in the level of ID-antibodies [5].

The aim of the study: To study cytokines in saliva and improve methods of noninvasive diagnosis of gastrointestinal allergy in children.

Materials and methods: To study the level of cytokines in saliva, 63 sick children from 3 to 10 years of age with GIA were examined, who were in the Bukhara Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center (BODMPMC) for examination and treatment.

Results and their discussion.

The study found a 5.8-fold increase in IL-8 (95.3 ± 6.12 pg/ml) with GIA in relation to the control - 16.2 ± 0.6 pg/ml. The study of secretory immunity in

patients with GIA showed a significant decrease in sIgA in both observation groups.

There was a significant decrease in sIgA by 3.7 times (0.3 ± 0.02 mg%) with GIA in relation to the control indicators - 1.1 ± 0.04 mg% ($P < 0.001$).

The concentration of IgE in saliva increases to 21.5 ± 1.29 mg% against the control - 1.2 ± 0.05 mg% ($P < 0.001$).

The study found a significant increase in the concentration of TNF- α in saliva in patients with GIA to - 60.8 ± 8.63 pg/ml versus control - 21.2 ± 1.0 pg/ml ($P < 0.01$).

Conclusions: Thus, based on the results of the study, a significant decrease in the level of salivator sIgA in patients with GIA was established. At the same time, there is a significant increase in the level of IdE, as well as salivatory proinflammatory cytokines- IL-8, TNF- α .

Secretory cytokines act as mediators in the implementation of the protective function of the body in bacterial, parasitic and viral infections. An increase in the concentration of secretory (soluble) cytokines in GIA indicates the comorbidity of its course and proves the need to exclude gastrointestinal pathology at the same time.

Consequently, the possibility of early diagnosis and differentiated management of sick children with GIA was obtained by the noninvasive method of determining salivator immunoglobulins and cytokines in pediatrics.

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